

SHORT FILMS AS A TOOL FOR STRENGTHENING LEARNERS' AUTONOMY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract

This study explores the use of short films as an educational tool to enhance 8th–9th grade students' autonomy in English language learning. The findings of the study show that using video materials helps learners stay motivated and understand new information more easily during English lessons.

Key words: short films, learner autonomy, independent learning, English language teaching, reflective thinking.

Annatation

This paper explores the role of short films as an instructional tool in the process of teaching English to school learners. The study focuses on how short film–based activities influence learners' motivation, comprehension, and self-development skills. To investigate this, a set of short films was integrated into classroom lessons, and students' responses, progress, and engagement were observed and analyzed. The findings show that short films create a meaningful and visually supported learning environment, helping learners understand language more easily and encouraging them to work independently. The research concludes that short films can be considered an effective supplementary resource for developing learners' linguistic skills and supporting their self-directed learning in English classes.

Key words: short films, investigate, English language learning, self-directed learning, motivation, comprehension.

Introduction.

In current English education, developing learners' autonomy is a fundamental goal. Students' autonomus learning enables students to take responsibility for their own progress, reflect on their achievements, and actively engage with language materials. Short films, owing to their visual, interactive, and motivational nature, serve as a powerful tool to support these skills. This research helps us to know how short films can be effectively used to enhance 8th–9th grade students' autonomy in English language learning.

Promoting learners' independent learning skills has become increasingly important in modern education. According to Mayer R. [1:304], video materials support cognitive processing by combining visual and auditory channels. Stempleski and Tomalin [2:176] argue that films enhance motivation and engagement. Richards and Renandya [3:422] point out that video-supported lessons provide meaningful input that facilitates comprehension and language skill development. These perspectives highlight the relevance of using short films to strengthen learner autonomy in English education. It is widely recognized that these scholars that promoting independent learning is crucial for today's learners. In my observation, the integration of short films not only supports cognitive processing, as Mayer suggests, but also creates a more engaging and motivating environment, in line with Stempleski and Tomalin . It is noticed that learners tend to participate more actively and reflect on their own progress

when video-based lessons are used. Therefore, It is considered that short films can serve as a practical and effective means to enhance learner autonomy and make English learning more meaningful, supporting .Richards and Renandya point about the value of meaningful input. Holec H. [4:53] states that learner autonomy is able to take charge of one's own learning, making decisions about content, pace, and methods, which perfectly be in line with the use of short films to encourage independent study. Zimmerman B. [5:64-70] also shows clearly that self-regulated learners set goals, track progress and reflect on outcomes, improving both motivation and learning efficiency. Building on the these ideas above mentioned , it can be observed that short films present a suitable method for using these concepts in real situations. In this context, students are able to understand with the content, meanings from situational cues, and make independent decisions about how to approach their learning. Such an approach not only strengthens motivation but also fosters confidence, experimentation, and a sense of responsibility for their own progress, making the learning process more meaningful and enjoyable.

The purpose of this study is to investigate how short films can be used to enhance 8th–9th grade students' autonomy in English language learning, fostering independent study habits, motivation, and reflective thinking.

The study employed the following methods: Classroom observation of lessons incorporating short films, semi-structured interviews with students to evaluate autonomy, analysis of video-based lesson activities and exercises, review of theoretical literature on autonomy and multimedia learning , comparison of experimental (short film-based) and traditional lessons. These methods enabled a comprehensive assessment of how short films affect learners' autonomous learning skills.

The research findings revealed that: short films significantly increase learners' motivation and attention during lessons because watching short films are more interesting than listening lecture , students demonstrate higher engagement and independent activity in addition when students can do tasks self-directly when that task will be understandable for them even when students do not fully understand all the words in short films, they are still able to grasp the meaning of the situations portrayed. This contextual understanding allows learners to infer meaning without relying on word-by-word translation, which is often the case with many students. Short films, therefore, provide a highly effective and convenient method for promoting comprehension, making lessons both engaging and motivating for learners. Video-based tasks promote reflective thinking and self-assessment, learners' autonomy and responsibility for their own learning improved, classroom environment became more interactive, meaningful, and learner-centered.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that short films, when purposefully integrated into English lessons, are an effective pedagogical tool for developing learners' autonomy.

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